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The Trump Effect: Readiness 2030, SAFE, and the German Debt Brake Reform

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Abstract*

The return of Donald Trump to the US Presidency in 2025 has dramatically impacted on the EU's fiscal framework. In response to Trump aims to disengage the US from guaranteeing the security of Europe, the EU has triggered the national safeguard clause of the Stability and Growth Pact (SGP), the center piece of the EU fiscal rules, reformed in 2024 after three years of suspension because of the pandemic. The decision exempts member states, for four years, from complying with the EU deficit rules for defense expenditures. At the same time, Germany, the member state championing fiscal stability, ditched decades of commitment to *Schwarze null*, and passed a constitutional amendment which enables annually spending of over 1% of gross domestic product (GDP) on defense in derogation of the *Schuldebremse*, the constitutional debt brake (formally remained operative for the other spending). The Trump effect thus led the EU to set aside again EU and national fiscal rules to increase defense spending. The outcome is an EU operating in a sort of fiscal limbo.

Keywords

Trump Presidency, EU fiscal integration, German fiscal policy, stability paradigm, security needs

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1. Introduction

The return of Donald Trump to the Presidency of the United States (US) on January 20, 2025, created shockwaves across the globe, upending the equilibria that for eight decades had governed international and transatlantic relations (Bond 2025; Walt 2025). The new US administration introduced massive reciprocal tariffs on trading partners, including the European Union (EU). It questioned the traditional American role in guaranteeing European security through the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO). Moreover, it shifted its policy towards the Russian war of aggression against Ukraine, opening bilateral diplomatic negotiations with the aggressor, the Russia's autocrat, Putin, and publicly berating Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelenski, the aggrieved, blaming him for starting the war. What are the effects of these extraordinary developments on the EU and its member states' ability to provide for their defense, an ability which requires the availability of fiscal resources for defense spending? This article focuses on the EU and the Economic and Monetary Union (EMU) framework of fiscal integration.

The article is structured as follows. Section 2 delineates the context. Section 3 maps the EU framework of fiscal integration, emphasizing the endurance of EU and national fiscal rules and the embryonic emergence of a fiscal capacity in response to Covid-19. Section 4 examines the Trump effect at EU level, analyzing the Commission's Readiness 2030 plan, with the suspension of the SGP to accommodate greater defense spending, and the proposal to set up SAFE. Section 5 examines the Trump effect at the German level, with the constitutional reform of the debt brake. Section 6 underlines the unsuitableness of the stability paradigm to guarantee the necessary fiscal resources for facing security needs. Section 7 shows how funding defense at the national level is likely to generate asymmetries between EU member states. One might plausibly argue that those asymmetries could trigger a further intervention for balancing them through some supranational capacities, according to a pattern known as "failing forward" (Jones, Kelemen, Meunier 2021), but this remains to be seen. Section 8 concludes.

2. The context

As stated in the Introduction by the editors of this special issue, by fiscal integration one should conceive "the policy mix of resources (fiscal capacity) and rules (fiscal regulation) (...) that characterizes EU fiscal governance after the recent pandemic and the war in the

Ukraine” (Zgaga, Wozniakowski, and Thomann 2025). The EU’s framework of fiscal integration, originally created by the 1992 Maastricht Treaty and developed during the following thirty years has been characterized by a model of fiscal regulation of member states’ fiscal capacity (Hallerberg 2013). The fiscal regulation’s model relies on fiscal rules enshrined both in EU laws, and in national constitutions, that constrain national budgetary policy to prevent negative externalities (Heipertz and Verdun 2010). The centerpiece of this regulatory framework is the Stability and Growth Pact (SGP), which reflected an ordo-liberal conception of economic policy (Hien & Joerges 2017). Because of the Covid-19 pandemic, the EU has suspended for three years the SGP (2020-2023) and acquired a centralized fiscal capacity, additional to the fiscal capacity of each of the member states and designed to cushion the shocks of an economic downturn (F. Fabbrini 2022). To finance the new program called Next Generation EU (NGEU), however, this fiscal capacity was temporary, with its resources distributed to the member states and not used by supranational institutions for generating European public goods (S. Fabbrini and Capati 2023; Buti, Coloccia, and Messori 2023). Being the fiscal capacity acquired during the pandemic “a big one-off” (Buti and S. Fabbrini 2023), the EU post-pandemic fiscal integration model returned to its fiscal regulation logic, although reformed in 2024 after the pandemic period’ suspension.

The reformed fiscal integration model has proven to be unsuited for dealing with the consequences of Trump policy towards Europe (defined here as the Trump effect), namely, to guarantee the necessary resources to the EU and its member states for providing for their own security. Not only do the EU and its member states need to spend more on their defense, but the EU member states, participating in NATO, have also specifically pledged (in the NATO summit held on June 25, 2025) to commit up to 5 per cent of their GDP to defense expenditure. To meet the challenges, on 4 March 2025 the Commission President Ursula von der Leyen proposed, as part of a so-called ReArm Europe plan, to suspend EU fiscal rules to allow member states to increase spending on defense. On 19 March 2025, the Commission, and the High Representative (2025) submitted a Joint White Paper for European Defense Readiness 2030 elaborating the rationale of the proposal. On the same day, the Commission (2025) detailed the conditions for accommodating increased defense expenditures within the reformed SGP through the activation of the so-called national escape clause in the SGP. This will exempt member states, for four years, from complying with the EU deficit rules for defense expenditures, making sure that countries that increase defense spending will not be subject to the EU excessive deficit procedure during this timeframe. The proposal expects an aggregate

increase of national defense expenditure of 650bn€. A new program has been also adopted: SAFE (Security Action for Europe), consisting of a 150bn€ fund that the Commission will raise from the financial markets, to provide loans to member states to support rearmament. Being loans, the funds, although provided at competitive interest rates, will need to be repaid by the beneficiaries. SAFE is a program expressing a new temporary fiscal capacity of the EU. Nevertheless, it is up to member states to decide how to use the SAFE funds.

At the same time, fiscal rules have been shelved in the EU member state that championed them most, Germany. Germany has been the crucial member state for promoting the fiscal regulation model thus adopted by the EU. In response to changes in the transatlantic relations, the Christian Democrats (CDU/CSU), which emerged victorious in the 23 February 2025 parliamentary elections, quickly struck a deal with the Social Democrats (SPD), as well as the Greens, to amend the constitutional balanced budget rule, the *Schuldenbremse*, a signature provision of the German Basic Law which prohibited borrowing. Since the parties of the new *Grosse Koalition*, CDU/CSU and SPD did not have a two-third majority in the newly elected Bundestag, even with the support of the Greens, they rushed the constitutional amendment in the outgoing Bundestag, which swiftly approved it on 18 March 2025. Following approval by the Bundesrat on 21 March 2025, the constitutional amendment entered into force on 23 March 2025, just a month since the start of the process. Ditching decades of commitment to *Schwarze null*, the constitutional amendment enables Germany to annually spend over 1% of gross domestic product (GDP) on defense in derogation of the *Schuldebremse*. At the same time, a new special 500bn€ fund has been created in derogation of the balanced budget constitutional rule for investment on infrastructure and the green transition.

The article provides a detailed legal and political analysis of the developments occurred in the March 2025, namely the Commission's Readiness 2030 plan with the suspension of the SGP, the SAFE program, and the German constitutional reform of the debt brake. Those developments were induced by a radical change in transatlantic relations, a crisis here conceptualized as a process rather than a moment in time (on the distinction between the two crises, see Brack and Gurkan 2021). The upending of 80 years of transatlantic relations, with uncertainties about the US security umbrella in Europe, put under dramatic pressure the EU fiscal regulation's model, leading to its suspension (or fiscal deregulation) at the national level (however only for defense), integrated by a limited central fiscal capacity (to support national rearmament). In fact, although the crisis has opened a window of opportunity for creating a central fiscal capacity to support a supranational defense system, the Commission, and the

governmental leaders of the most influential countries (as France, Germany, Italy) used the window of opportunity for strengthening national defense spending. This development openly contradicts the Riker's model which postulates that confederations (or unions of states) tend to centralize under the pressure of a threat. Riker wrote (1975: 116), "in every successfully formed federalism it must be the case that a significant external or internal threat or a significant opportunity for aggression is present, where the threat can be forestalled, and the aggression carried out only with a bigger government". Facing the Russian threat without the US protection, the EU, instead, moved in the opposite direction. It decentralized rather than centralized its model of fiscal governance. Fiscal deregulation (although within specific rules) for defense will lead to an increased nationalization of the latter, wrapped within a policy coordination approach, confirming the confederal/intergovernmental nature of the EU defense system. This nationalization will likely create asymmetries between member states because the latter have different fiscal spaces to spend on defense and have different defense capabilities. As argued by the editors of this special issue (Zgaga, Wozniakowski, and Thomann 2025), this leaves the EU and its member states in a fiscal limbo. By fiscal limbo one must understand a context where the old fiscal rules are unusable, and the new ones temporarily limited. The exit of policymaking in times of crisis (Baumgartner and Bonafont 2025) is generally unpredictable, but this is even more true in a security crisis which reaches to the existence itself of the EU.

3. The EU framework of fiscal regulation

As a large body of literature has pointed out, fiscal regulation through binding rules has been an essential feature of EMU since its inception with the 1992 Treaty of Maastricht (Heipertz and Verdun 2020; Dyson and Featherstone 1999). Indeed, as James (2012) pointed out, EMU emerged from a political compromise between France and Germany, which insisted on introducing reference values and procedural requirements for national budgetary policy to avoid a transfer union. This was seen as crucial because EMU was not an optimal currency area. In fact, the transfer of monetary policy to a federal European Central Bank (ECB) coexisted with decentralized fiscal policies in the EMU member states. The adoption of a constellation of fiscal rules constraining member states' budgetary policies was thus regarded as necessary to prevent negative externalities -- the "moral hazard" problem (Mundell 1961).

Fiscal rules were introduced both at EU and national level. At EU level, the bulwark of fiscal regulation is the SGP, initially approved in 1997 and currently enshrined in Protocol No.

12 of the EU Treaties. The SGP introduced clear numerical rules that member states must follow in their budgetary policy, namely an obligation to maintain annual deficit below 3% of gross domestic product (GDP), and to lower debts below 60% of GDP. EU primary law also introduced a procedure, currently codified in Article 126 TFEU, to correct excessive deficit, which empowers the Commission to monitor member states' public finances and foresee the possibility to sanction a member state which ran afoul of EU fiscal rules. These rules are then further spelled out in EU secondary legislation, which have detailed procedural mechanisms and specific criteria applicable to member states which are at risk of violating the deficit and debt rule (the so-called preventive arm of the SGP) and member states which are already in breach of them (the so-called corrective arm of the SGP).

On national level, instead, fiscal rules emerged in response to the sovereign debt crisis, and took the form of balanced budget constitutional requirement. The driving force of this process was Germany, which in 2009 amended its Basic Law to introduce a *Schuldebremse*, a debt brake. In response to the deterioration of public finances resulting from the sovereign debt crisis, Germany committed to a fiscal rule even stricter than the one set at EU level. Specifically, Article 109(3) Basic Law was amended to provide that, "(t)he budgets of the Federation and the Länder shall, in principle, be balanced without revenue from credits." Furthermore, the same provision, jointly with the amended Article 115 Basic Law, also made clear that the balanced budget requirement for the federal budget "shall be deemed to be satisfied if revenue from credits does not exceed 0.35[% of GDP]", while tout court prohibiting a deficit to the budget of the Länder.

The German model of constitutionalizing a balance budget requirement did not remain confined to that member state. In response to the sovereign debt crisis, under the leadership of Chancellor Angela Merkel, Germany insisted that other EMU member states follow the same template. In fact, the 2012 Treaty on Stability, Coordination and Governance in EMU, usually known as the Fiscal Compact, compelled precisely that. The core provision of the Fiscal Compact, Article 3, introduced an obligation for contracting parties to constitutionalize a golden rule in their national constitutions. Specifically, Article 3(1)(a) set the general rule that "the budgetary position of the general government of a Contracting Party shall be balanced or in surplus", with the clarification that this requirement will be considered as respected if deficit does not exceed 0.5% of GDP, save for the possibility to deviate from this convergence path in case of exceptional circumstances. Furthermore, Article 3(2) stated that "[t]he rules set out in paragraph 1 shall take effect in the national law of the Contracting Parties [...] through

provisions of binding force and permanent character, preferably constitutional, or otherwise guaranteed to be fully respected and adhered to throughout the national budgetary process.” Describing the Fiscal Compact, Besselink and Reestman (2012) affirmed that through it “Europe was speaking German”. In fact, several member states including Italy introduced balanced budget requirements in their constitutions.

The global pandemic forced the EU to adjust its framework of fiscal regulation. In response to Covid-19 the EU suspended for the first time ever the fiscal rules of the SGP for three years, from 2020 to 2023, empowering member states to increase public deficit to cushion the economic shock caused by the pandemic (Estella 2021). Moreover, the EU established new financial programs, notably a system to support employment re-insurance, known as SURE, and then the Next Generation EU (NGEU), which ultimately led to the establishment of a temporary centralized EU fiscal capacity (Wozniakowski 2023; F. Fabbrini 2022). NGEU empowers the Commission to issue 800bn€ of common debt, and to transfer this to member states (in form of loans and/or grants) according to the social and economic costs of the pandemic, to support their post-pandemic economic recovery, with a long-term plan to repay the debt with common EU taxes (own resources). As such, NGEU vests in the EU new borrowing at the supranational level and spending at the national one. There are differences between the two programs. SURE operated in the form of back-to-back loans, with national guarantees, which member states had to repay, albeit at favorable terms (Cooper 2024). NGEU is time-limited as funding was clearly defined as exceptional and will come to an end in 2026. As Buti and S. Fabbrini (2023) argued, the time-limited nature of NGEU can be explained by the politics of its approval, and especially Germany’s opposition towards a permanent fiscal capacity.

The pandemic did not end the “governing by rules and rules by number in the Eurozone” (Schmidt 2020). Following the three years suspension of the SGP during Covid-19 and its immediate aftermath, the EU reintroduced a revised SGP in 2024. Through a package of two regulations and a directive, the EU institutions adjusted both the corrective and the preventive arm of the SGP, with the aim to simplify the legal framework and replace the old rules’ one-size-fits-all with more tailored-made national pathways to reduce deficit and debt. Specifically, regulation (EU) 2024/1263 on effective coordination of economic policies introduced the key criteria of net expenditure and required member states to lay out a medium-term fiscal-structural plans to reduce net expenditure over a 4-year adjustment period, which could be extended to 7 years in case of relevant set of reforms and investments (Pench 2024). Yet, the

revised SGP reaffirmed the rationale of the fiscal regulation model, although it was made more flexible.

At the national level, taking Germany as the bellwether, the fiscal framework remained largely untouched. In 2022, when the SGP was suspended, the Government of Chancellor Olaf Scholz approved, through a constitutional revision, the creation of a special, one-off 100bn€ fund, financed through debt, to upgrade the German federal army. This measure, which was part of the *Zeitenwende* following Russia's aggression of Ukraine (Scholz 2023), has been implemented only slowly because of the persistence of the stability paradigm. Furthermore, efforts to increase public spending were struck down by the German Constitutional Court (BVerfG), based on the *Schuldenbremse*. In 2023 the BVerfG declared unconstitutional and void Germany's second supplementary budget act of 2021, which provided for the transfer of an authorization to borrow €60bn, granted in response to the Covid-19 pandemic and not needed in 2021, to the Energy and Climate Fund, since renamed the Climate and Transformation Fund (BVerfG 2023). On a legal challenge from the opposition, the BVerfG ruled that the government and the parliamentary majority had violated the constitutional debt break by authorizing additional borrowing for Covid-19 related purpose, but shifting these resources to a different political objective, namely the promotion of climate protection and transformation resulting from the energy crisis caused by Russia's war in Ukraine. The BVerfG ruling, however, caused a €60bn hole in the government's budget, and confirmed the unwavering abidance to fiscal rules (Financial Times 2023).

4. The Trump effect at EU level: the national escape clause of the SGP and SAFE

The return of President Trump for a second term created an earthquake for the EU fiscal integration regime. As the new US administration openly treated Europe as an adversary, NATO as a burden and Russia as a partner, the EU and its member states were hastily forced to react. This resulted in the forced freezing of the fiscal regulation model to allow increased national spending on defense and military rearmament, complemented by a program allowing the Commission to collect resources on the financial market to transfer to national governments promoting joint projects of re-armament.

Although the EU had increased its defense resources to help Ukraine to stand Russia's aggression (F. Fabbrini 2025), the Trump effect exposed the weaknesses of the EU and its member states' military capability, thus pushing EU policymakers to devise an unprecedented

plan for continental re-armament. This plan is centered on the suspension of EU fiscal rules to facilitate defense expenditure. Commission President Ursula von der Leyen first put forward the idea of “unleashing the use of public funding in defense” to ramp up defense spending in a letter sent to heads of state and government on 4 March 2025, ahead of a European Council meeting. In this letter, the Commission outlined a plan, then labelled ReArm Europe, based on five points, namely: (1) the activation of the SGP escape clause to enable greater national spending in defense; (2) the creation of a special 150bn€ fund to provide loans to member states to ramp up defense expenditures; (3) the possibility to re-allocate cohesion policy funding on defense; (4) the expansion of the European Investment Bank (EIB)’s mandate on defense; and (5) the mobilization of private capital. The European Council on 6 March 2025 endorsed the Commission proposal, inviting it also to explore additional sources of common funding (European Council 2025, para 6a), and the European Parliament also welcome it in a non-binding resolution adopted on 12 March 2025 (European Parliament 2025, para 76).

On 19 March 2025, the Commission jointly with the High Representative further detailed the plan, relabeling the part concerning rearmament as European Readiness 2030, in a Joint White Paper on European Defense Readiness (European Commission and High Representative 2025). In conjunction with this, the Commission released a communication on accommodating increased defense expenditure within the SGP, detailing the first point of the Readiness 2030 plan (European Commission 2025a). Moreover, the Commission also published a proposal for a Council regulation establishing a special 150bn€ fund to provide loans to member states to ramp up defense expenditure, SAFE, thus advancing a legislative text to operationalize the second point of the Readiness 2030 plan (European Commission 2025b).

The communication on accommodating increased defense expenditure within the SGP (European Commission 2025a), which is only 7 pages long, begins by stating that “[i]n a context of heightened geopolitical tensions [...] Europe must urgently step up its defense capabilities” and acknowledges that this “require[s] an urgent increase in European defense spending” (Ibid, 1). Consequently, the communication affirms that the impact of “higher level of defense expenditure on Member States’ budgets can be accommodated [...] through the flexibility provided within the existing EU fiscal framework” (Ibid). Specifically, “in view of the extraordinary situation, the Commission proposes to unlock additional flexibility for higher defense spending through a coordinated activation of the national escape clause” (Ibid, 2) enshrined in Article 26 of regulation (EU) 2024/1263, the preventive arm of the SGP. This

provision empowers the Council, acting by qualified majority (QMV), following a request from a member state and a recommendation by the Commission, to allow a member state to deviate from its net expenditure path “where exceptional circumstances outside the control of the Member State have a major impact on the public finances of the Member States concerned.”

According to the Commission, circumstances allow for triggering the national escape clause. In the communication on accommodating increased defense expenditure within the SGP, the Commission calls on “all Member States” to make use of the flexibility activating their national escape clause “in a coordinated manner” (Ibid) and invites national governments “to come forward with the request to activate the national escape clause by the end of April [2025]” (Ibid, 7). As the Commission makes clear, the activation of the national escape clause allows member states to deviate from the net expenditure path, which requires lowering the national deficit in the medium-term. This means that member states will be legally authorized to indebt themselves to a much greater degree for meeting their defense needs. Furthermore, the activation of the national escape clause means that a member state breaching the SGP criteria, with a deficit over 3% of GDP, will not be subjected to the excessive deficit procedure for the following four years.

In its communication, the Commission endeavors to delimit SGP flexibility only for higher defense expenditure. First, in terms of scope, the communication states that “the flexibility would cover the increase of total defense expenditure, including both investment and current expenditure” (Ibid, 4). Specifically, the Commission defines which statistical category of public expenditure falls under the exception, using a classification which is close to that used by NATO to measure defense expenditure. Second, in terms of size, the communication states that the flexibility under the national escape clause “should be capped at 1.5% of GDP, compared to the net expenditure path” of each member state, with the aim to secure fiscal sustainability (Ibid, 5). Third, in terms of duration, the communication foresees that the activation of the national escape clause for defense expenditure will be available “for a period of four years, starting in 2025” (Ibid, 6). Yet the communication affirms that the reference year to calculate increase in defense expenditure will retroactively be 2021, to reward “Member States that have already ramped up their defense spending since the start of Russia’s war of aggression against Ukraine” (Ibid).

The Commission proposal for a Council regulation establishing a special 150bn€ fund (SAFE), instead, was quickly approved by the Council and entered into force in May 2025 as Council Regulation (EU) 2025/1106. SAFE constitutes a temporary central fiscal capacity,

funded by resources raised in the financial markets by the European Commission. It is based on Article 122 TFEU, which allows the Council to “decide, in a spirit of solidarity between Member States, upon the measures appropriate to the economic situation” and to provide financial assistance to a member state in case, among others, of “exceptional occurrences beyond its control”.

Pursuant to Article 1, the Council regulation establishes SAFE and sets out conditions and procedures under which financial assistance shall be provided to and implemented by the member states. In terms of objective, SAFE is designed to provide funding for the procurement of key military capabilities, including ammunition and missiles, artillery systems, drones, air and missile defense and strategic enablers. As specified in Article 2(3), to access SAFE funding member states must proceed with “joint procurement”: a member state can request support provided it uses the funds to purchase military capabilities jointly with another EU member state, Ukraine or third countries “with whom the Union has entered a Security and Defense Partnership”. Article 17 further details the conditions for third country participation in the program. On the other hand, Article 16 provides that the value of the contract shall not include material produced outside the EU for a percentage exceeding 35%. However, compared to the original Commission proposal, the Council insisted on introducing an exception to joint purchasing: pursuant to Article 4(3), in fact, member states are also allowed to individually and unilaterally proceed with autonomous purchasing for a whole year, until 30 May 2026, in derogation from the joint purchasing rule.

From a funding perspective, Article 9 of the regulation enables the Commission to borrow funds on the financial markets, but as clearly indicated in Article 5 this is up to a maximum of 150bn€. From a governance perspective, SAFE follows the legal technology of NGEU. According to Article 7 of the regulation, member states must present a “European defense industry investment plan”, with the description of the defense products need, and the description of the planned activities to ramp up defense production. As indicated in Article 12, member state can request loan financing to the Commission “until 31 December 2030.” Pursuant to Article 8, the Commission “shall assess” national plans, and decide on the request for financial assistance. Once the national plan has been assessed positively, as indicated in Article 10, the Commission and member states will enter into a loan agreement and operational arrangements, and pursuant to Article 11 the Commission can disburse to the relevant member state a pre-financing payment. However, as indicated in Article 12, the Commission will regularly monitor advancement with the implementation of the national defense plan,

authorizing the disbursement of periodic installments only if there has been progress in the implementation of national investment plans in the defense industry, which, pursuant to Article 18, may also include changes to existing contracts or framework agreements. SAFE, finally, introduces regular monitoring, reporting and communication requirements, with the application of rules on classified and sensitive information.

The Readiness 2030 plan marks the suspension of the stability paradigm. The Commission decision to accommodate increased defense spending through the activation of the national escape clause of the SGP effectively mutes EU fiscal rules to enable greater national investment on defense. At the same time, with SAFE, the EU acquires a limited fiscal capacity to financially support, in the form of loans, member states pursuing joint procurement projects of defense products – although for an initial transition period of one year SAFE funding can also be used by each member state on its own.

5. The Trump effect at German level: amending the constitution

While the Trump effect prompted the EU to overhaul its fiscal regulation model, it has imposed important developments in the country that supported that model more than anyone else: Germany. In late November 2024, the three-party coalition (SPD, the Greens, and the Free Democratic Party or FDP) collapsed because of a dispute over the next budget. In the snap elections held on 23 February 2025, the CDU/CSU under the leadership of Friedrich Merz won the plurality vote and immediately entered negotiations with the SPD to form a *Grosse Koalition*. Reacting to the action of Trump, the two parties quickly reneged on pledges made during the electoral campaign and agreed to amend the constitutional balanced budget obligation to increase spending on defense and investment on infrastructure and domestic industry. At the same time, since the CDU/CSU and the SPD (even with the help of the Greens) did not have, in the newly elected Bundestag, the 2/3 majority required to approve a constitutional amendment, they decided to use the outgoing legislature's lower chamber (the Bundestag), which was formally in office until 23 March 2025, to modify the *Schuldenbremse*. While this decision raised the issue of legitimacy, it stood from the point of view of legality. In fact, the BVerfG rejected as inadmissible the constitutional complaint raised by the opposition party *Alternative für Deutschland* (AfD) which tried to suspend the convocation of the Bundestag.

Consequently, the German Parliament was summoned for a special session, and thanks to a cross-party agreement reached between the CDU/CSU, the SPD, and the Greens, which set aside additional funding for climate transition, on 18 March 2025 the Bundestag approved by a majority of 513-to-207 (no abstention) the revision of the Basic Law (the Bundestag has 733 members, and a constitutional revision required a two-third majority, hence 489 aye). Subsequently, on 21 March 2025, the Bundesrat, the upper chamber of the German legislature, which represents the 16 federal Länder, also approved with a 53-to-16 majority (abstention counting as negative vote) the constitutional revision (the Bundesrat has 69 votes, and a constitutional revision required a two-third majority, hence 46 aye). Following the signature by the federal President Frank-Walter Steinmeier and its publication on the *Bundesgesetzblatt* on 22 March 2025 (Gesetz zur Änderung des Grundgesetzes 2025), the groundbreaking constitutional reform entered into force in less than one month since the Bundestag election.

Specifically, the German constitutional revision introduced a new sentence in Article 109(3) Basic Law, and amended with identical words also Article 115(2) Basic Law, stating that “the amount by which defense expenditures exceed 1 percent of nominal gross domestic product shall be deducted from the income from loans to be taken into account.” This effectively allows the German federal government to indebt itself over 1% of GDP on defense expenditure outside the restriction of the debt brake, which as mentioned above constrained deficit to 0.35% of GDP. Furthermore, reflecting the political compromise between the CDU/CSU, which pushed for greater spending on defense, and the SPD and the Greens, which pushed for greater spending on social policy and the climate transition, the constitutional reform introduced in the Basic Law a new Article 143h, which enabled “the Federation [to] establish a special fund with its own borrowing authority for investments in infrastructure with a volume of up to €500 billion”, outside the constraints of the *Schuldebremse*, of which 100bn€ will be allocated to the Länder. Finally, in a political move designed to secure the support of the Bundesrat for the constitutional amendment, the revision empowered the Länder to also run annual deficits up to 0.35% of GDP, like the federal government.

Germany’s approval of the constitutional reform of the debt break has been dubbed by the new Chancellor Friedrich Merz as a “whatever it takes moment” (Kirby 2025), in a clear reference to the speech that the then ECB President Mario Draghi gave in July 2012, and which proved to be essential to save EMU during the sovereign debt crisis. By exempting any defense spending over and above 1% of GDP from the debt brake, the constitutional reform effectively permits Germany to significantly borrow to strengthen its defense, with early estimates

suggesting that the country may invest 1tn€ on defense within a decade (Kinkartz 2025). This open-ended exemption fundamentally weakens the logic of the *Schuldenbremse*, which is formally preserved in the Basic Law but practically emptied. Furthermore, since defense spending traditionally drives economic growth, with impact on industrial policy and employment, the reform might inject a Keynesian turn in the German economic model. As pointed out by Deutsche Bank Research (2025), “this is one of the most historic paradigm shifts in German postwar history. Both the speed at which this is happening, and the magnitude of the prospective fiscal expansion is reminiscent of German reunification.”

6. Security and the stability paradigm

The developments occurred at EU and German level, because of Donald Trump’s policy towards Europe, have shown the unsuitableness of the stability paradigm, introduced by the 1992 Maastricht Treaty, for accommodating growing defense expenditures (Zgaga 2026). In its 1993 *Maastricht Urteil*, the German Constitutional Court upheld the constitutionality of the Maastricht Treaty on the grounds that it created a stability union (BVerfG 1993). Furthermore, the concern for stability was at the heart of the response to the sovereign debt crisis, as evidence by the adoption of the 2012 Treaty on Stability, Coordination and Governance in the EU, the Fiscal Compact, and indeed by the reform of the SGP. Stability inspired also the establishment of bailout mechanisms in response to that crisis, notably the European Stability Mechanism (ESM) in 2013. In its *Pringle* ruling, the European Court of Justice (ECJ 2013) upheld the compatibility of the ESM with the EU Treaties on the argument that it fostered stability, and that it provided support to member states in the forms of loans, subjected to strict conditionality. Also, the EU response to Covid-19 did not fundamentally challenge the stability paradigm of EMU: while the EU suspended (temporarily) the SGP and created a (temporary) centralized fiscal capacity through NGEU, it confirmed the centrality of fiscal rules designed to constrain national budgetary policy by reforming the SGP in 2023-4.

Security concerns had been largely absent from the operation of EMU. In 2014, when Russia illegally seized Crimea, NATO, under the leadership of then US President Barack Obama, requested European allies to increase defense spending to at least 2% of GDP. Moreover, during his first term, President Trump had made clear that he expected NATO European allies to increase the burden of their defense and questioned the mutual defense pledge at the heart of the transatlantic alliance. Nevertheless, EU member states systematically

failed to increase their defense spending. Russia's large-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022, with the return of conventional warfare on the European continent on a scale unseen since World War II, eventually led to a slow but steady increase of national funding for defense. Yet, before the arrival of Trump at the White House in January 2025, Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine did not fundamentally alter the stability paradigm of the EU fiscal framework. At the EU level, the issue hardly emerged in the SGP revision process in 2023-4. Despite calls in this direction, the preventive arm of the new SGP limited itself to referring to "where necessary, the build-up of defense capabilities" as one of the elements to be included in national mid-term fiscal-structural plans (Regulation 2024/1263 Article 13(c)(iv)).

This approach was shaken by the Trump effect. The EU has had to suddenly prioritize security concerns. At EU level, the European Commission suspended the application of the SGP regarding defense spending, while the Council approved a special fund, SAFE, to support the national ramp-up of defense production. At the national level, in Germany, a "fiscal revolution" (Bofinger 2025) has occurred in just a month with the Parliament revising the constitutional debt break to effectively enable unlimited borrowing for defense. The combined effect of these developments is that, for the first time since its establishment, EMU is no longer subjected to strict fiscal rules. It is true that, during Covid-19 and its aftermath, the SGP was suspended, but fiscal rules remained in place at national level (Quaglia and Verdun 2023), as the nullification of the German budget act for 2023 proved. Now, Germany, the champion of the fiscal regulation's model, has freed itself from fiscal rules, opening a path also for other member states.

Because of the Trump effect, defense spending has become a priority for the EU and its member states. However, under the pressure of national governments, the Commission has awarded member states more rooms for spending on national defense. However, the ability of member states to increase their deficit for defense spending will be uneven since they have different fiscal spaces at their disposal. If member states with high debt levels decide to spend on defense, they will be constrained by financial markets, as well as by the fiscal rules that will restart after the suspension period. After all, as Kelemen and Teo pointed out (2014), fiscal rules were never by themselves the only constraints on member states' budgetary action. Fiscal rules served as focal points for financial markets, who increase borrowing costs for member states failing to comply with self-imposed budgetary targets (Matthijs 2020). The pressure of financial markets will not decrease on highly indebted member states now that EU fiscal rules are suspended. The muting of fiscal rules is nonetheless significant as it alters the framework

of fiscal integration, acknowledging that security is an expensive task which requires spending on a multi-year basis to guarantee it.

In its communication on accommodating increased defense spending within the SGP, the European Commission (2025a) states that “Russia’s war of aggression against Ukraine and its threat to European security are exceptional circumstances outside the control of Member States, which have a major impact on Member States’ public finances through the related incurred and/or planned increase in defense expenditure” (Ibid 2). But this is an improbable and unconvincing justification for activating the escape clause in the SGP. Russia’s large-scale invasion of Ukraine had started three years before, on February 24, 2022. Moreover, Russia’s had already illegally seized Crimea in February 2014. The real change that explains why the European Commission activated the SGP escape clause was the return of Donald Trump to the US Presidency, and the consequential unraveling of the transatlantic relationship. As German Chancellor Merz assessed on 23 February 2025, the German constitutional debt brake had to go because US military protection can no longer be taken for granted. Europe had to step up, including by providing for its own defense, thus becoming independent from the US (see also Zgaga 2025, this special issue).

The suspension of the SGP and the reform of the debt-brake clause of the German basic law confirm that a balanced-budget policy is hardly compatible with having defense capability and the need to maintain it through time. Historically, nation states have used debt to finance standing armies, with which to wage war, ensure peace, and more generally to protect themselves (Tilly 1975). In unions of states as US, as Wozniakowski (2025, this special issue) writes, it was indirect taxation which made possible “the development of fiscal capacity during the 19th century (...) enabling the federal government to finance common defense and its territorial expansion”. It is no coincidence that the US has never had a balanced budget requirement in its federal constitution and has regularly had a spending deficit, although contained by a debt ceiling negotiated between the House of Representatives and the Senate. The US federated states introduced, since the 1840s, balanced budget rules to guarantee the confidence of financial markets to which they had to resort to meeting their financial needs (Rodden 2006), but the federal government has never been subjected to a *Schwarze null* clause, a situation which allowed the country to finance, after WWII, the most powerful army globally (*inter alia*). But in their illusion of “perpetual peace” Germany and the EU had believed they could focus only on *Schwarze null*, leaving the financial burden of their security to the US (Kagan 2003). With Trump, the EU and Germany have wakened up to the dark reality of hard

power, having to question the stability paradigm to deal with defense needs, re-armament and strategic autonomy. However, they have done so through the nationalization of defense and its corresponding fiscal bases.

7. National v. EU Defense: The Asymmetries' Trap

Having to deal with the necessity to provide for their own security, EU member states' governments called for additional resources for defense, which would have been prevented by the fiscal regulation model of the SGP. The Commission answered those pressures with the Readiness 2020 plan: this, in particular, enabled the suspension of the SGP for four years, while specifying that, to safeguard fiscal sustainability, national defense spending should be “up to a maximum of 1,5 per cent of GDP for each year of activation of the national escape clause (and) for a period of four year”. At the same time, through SAFE, the Commission and Council mobilized 150bn€ in support of national rearmament. Thus, both programs aim to incentive *national* defense spending in defense. This approach for promoting a rearmament of the EU based on national empowerment, however, is bound to create defense asymmetries between member states, making the new approach systemically fragile. Two asymmetries can be identified – and indeed are already emerging in practice.

First, Readiness 2030 is going to generate industrial asymmetries, because not all member states are ready to profit from the possibility to spend more on defense (as argued by Buti & Messori, this special issue). The possibility of more defense spending can be used only by member states with low public debt (Germany and other Nordic countries), not by member states with high public debt (Italy, France, and the southern countries). What is allowed by legal rules, is not necessarily allowed by financial markets (Matthijs and Blyth 2015). In fact, as of 2025, only 16 EU member states have decided to activate the national escape clause of the SGP, and, except for Germany, none of the other 3 big EU member states (France, Italy and Spain) did so (Council 2025). It is risky for highly indebted member states to increase their debt through more spending on defense: so these may prefer pursuing a free-ride strategy. The same is partially true for SAFE. It is true that the Commission launched a program providing loans to highly indebted member states at lower interest rates that they may get by directly financing on the financial markets: Yet, although at favorable conditions those loans need to be repaid. As a result, as reported by the Commission, 19 member states have requested SAFE support (European Commission 2025c). Thus, in industrial and technological terms, the low public debt

member states would receive a bust from the suspension of the stability paradigm, while this will not be the case for the high public debt member states. Certainly, the increased spending on defense by the low public debt member states will have a likely multiplier effect on their domestic production, with positive implications also for the indebted member states industrially connected to them through the value-chain. However, an industrial hierarchy among member states is not a condition for the spreading of technological innovations. The innovation's possibilities will be high in low public debt and low in high public debt member states. Instead of having a cohesive union in defense, divisions between member states will be the likely outcome.

Second, Readiness 2030, as part of the Joint White Paper for European Defense, assumes that, in military terms, member states' capabilities should be coordinated at the intergovernmental level. Member states should be helped "to identify EU-level capability shortfalls and priorities" and to enhance their "cooperation through the Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO) to implement capability and operational defense projects". The EU should thus operate as a supporting structure for the member states, offering them an arena (through the European Council or the Foreign Affairs Council) where to cooperate, in the context of the Common Security and Defense Policy and with the support of the European Defense Agency connected to the latter. However, it is unlikely that intergovernmental military coordination might overcome asymmetries and deliver European deterrence: after all, even the self-selective PESCO has not met its end so far (indeed, 26 out of 27 member states are part of it). If, in general, asymmetries are structural in the EU, because they reflect member states' different demographic size and culture, they are even deeper in the security field, because of the deep difference in military capabilities and defense necessities (Howorth 2014). The perception of the threat can differ substantially between member states. Russia is a threat for the eastern member states but may be an economic opportunity for the southern member states. Intergovernmental coordination makes inconceivable the identification of an EU interest in defense, distinct from the specific national interests of its member states. Because of the status of France as a nuclear power and international actor (with a seat in the UN Security Council), it is likely that it will claim to be the leading country in security policy, with the support of Germany on the economic field. French leadership, however, will not be easily accepted by eastern or neutralist or Atlanticist member states. Security asymmetries, in an intergovernmental context, generate hierarchies in favor of the larger and stronger member states and free-riding behavior by the smaller and weaker member states, unless they are

controlled by a higher power as has been the case of the US in NATO. Divisions between member states will be the likely outcome of the nationalization's approach in defense.

Following Jones, Kelemen, and Meunier (2021), one might argue that the two asymmetries will end up jeopardizing the aim of creating a more secure EU, thus triggering a pressure for balancing them through supranational measures leading to a central fiscal capacity. It is the logic of "failing forward" that can be falsified only over time. Following S. Fabbrini (2025), instead, it may be time for the EU to rethink its structures in a more federalist way.

8. Conclusions

The article has examined the Trump effect on the fiscal regulation model adopted at both the EU and the national level since the Maastricht Treaty, with Germany as the pioneer in elaborating and diffusing it. The fiscal regulation model has been suspended temporally, being unviable for dealing with the security concerns raised by Trump's approach to Putin's Russia and its challenge to transatlantic relations. Because security has become the priority of the EU agenda, the Commission enabled the activation of the national safeguard clause of the SGP, although temporally, while Germany reformed its constitutional debt brake.

Because of the radical change of US policy towards Europe, EU has decided to let the member states spend more on defense (through Readiness 2030). While traditionally EMU has been founded on the stability paradigm, the latest developments in security have called into question the SGP and national debt brake rules, without questioning however the pre-eminence of member states in security. In fact, although decisions have been adopted to increase defense spending and re-armament, to face a threat, represented by Putin's Russia, that is not contingent, the increase concerns national and not supranational defense systems. Because the security umbrella traditionally provided by the US through NATO is no longer certain, the Commission suspended the fiscal regulation model considered for long an economic orthodoxy, with the purpose to increase public spending for defense at the national level, with the aim to strengthening their defense capabilities, their military readiness, and their ability to deter autonomously a possible enemy attack.

The EU has made short-term choices without considering their medium-term consequences, as epitomized by Readiness 2030 which differentiates national defense' systems based on their national fiscal space. Nationalization of defense (Readiness 2030) and a temporary fiscal capacity at the center (SAFE), together with the reform of the German

Schuldenbremse, mark certainly a turning point from the ordoliberal faith in fiscal rules. However, their asymmetric consequences will not plausibly guarantee the irreversibility of the turning point. The muting of the SGP and the reform of the German basic law, in response to the changing security context, has not led to the creation of a central fiscal capacity, except for a 150bn€ common fund, called SAFE. Although fiscal regulation has been suspended twice and although forms of temporary central fiscal capacity have been introduced twice, no proposal has been advanced for making fiscal regulation and fiscal capacity compatible on a permanent basis, since the threat to European security is not contingent.

Thus, the EU and its member states are operating in a fiscal limbo, with the old rules suspended and the new ones introduced for only a limited period. With the latter strengthening the national rather than supranational fiscal capacity, the EU is contradicting the Riker's model.

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